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THE IMPACT OF MILD ANEMIA ON COGNITIVE FUNCTIONS OF ELDERLY PATIENTS WITH COGNITIVE IMPAIRMENT OR DEMENTIA OF VASCULAR OR ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE ORIGIN

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Abstract

Anemia is frequent in elderly with cognitive decline. The aim of our study was to examine the association between anemia and cognitive functioning among elderly patients with AD, VD and mixed AD and VD (mixed dementia, MD).

Material and methods: We examined 38 cognitive impaired patients with mild anemia (80.0±6.76 years old, 14 males and 24 females, 11 with AD, 12 with VD and 15 with MD) and 108 cognitive impaired patients without anemia (75.55±7.39 years old, 34 males and 74 females, 27 with AD, 44 with VD and 24 with MD) with the following neuropsychological battery Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE), Isaac's Set Test (IST), Literal fluency Test (LFT), Clock Drawing Test (CDT), 10 Words Test, Digit Symbol Substitution test (DSST 90sec), Digit Span Test (DST forward and backward) twice over a period of 2 years. All results were interpreted at 95% confidential level.

Results: Patients with anemia showed lower MMSE, IST, LFT, CDT and DSST test results vs those without. There were correlations between serum hemoglobin level and MMSE (reciprocal), IST (reciprocal), LFT (linear), CDT (sqr. root), DSST (sqr. root or linear) test performances.

Conclusions: Anemia is frequent in elderly patients with cognitive deficits and dementia. The existence of anemia is associated with additional executive dysfunction in such patients.

Keywords: anemia, cognitive impairment, elderly, executive functions.

The frequency of anemia among elderly is about 35%. It is even more frequent among those over 80 years of age, patients with diabetes mellitus, with gate impairments, visual problems or dependent from caregivers (Krishnapillai, 2015). Anemia, itself, is associated with cognitive impairments and dementia (Choi, 2020; Gattas, 2020; Weiss, 2022; Fehsel, 2023). Possible causative relations found between anemia and serum iron deficiency and development of Alzheimer's disease (AD), although the exact mechanism is unclear (Andreev, 2020; Gattas 2020; Lei, 2021; Fehsel, 2023). Anemia is a risk factor for development of brain vascular disease (VD) and worsening of small vessels disease (Wolters, 2019; Fonseca, 2021).

The aim of our study was to examine the association between anemia and cognitive functioning among elderly patients with AD, VD and mixed AD and VD (mixed dementia, MD).

Material and methods

We examined 38 cognitive impaired patients with mild anemia (80.0±6.76 years old, 14 males and 24 females, 11 with AD, 12 with VD and 15 with MD) and 108 cognitive impaired patients without anemia (75.55±7.39 years old, 34 males and 74 females, 27 with AD, 44 with VD and 24 with MD).

The inclusion criteria of the study were 1. Age ≥ 60 years; 2. Confirmed by neuropsychologist cognitive impairment at ≥2 cognitive domains; 3. Confirmed on the basis of history, neurological and somatic examination, laboratory data and imaging study diagnosis of AD or SVD or MD; 4. HB level above 100g/l; 5. No active oncologic disease; 6. Lack of other neurological diseases such as trauma, brain tumors, neuroinfections,

demyelinating diseases or epilepsy; 7. Lack of decompensation of coexisted somatic diseases during the study; 8. Lack of psychiatric diseases, except of mild depression or anxiety; 9. Lack of treatment or usage of benzodiazepines, modafinil acetate, hallucinogens and other psychoactive drugs, except for low dosages of Quetiapine (≤50mg/d), Pregabalin (≤150mg/d), Gabapentin (≤600mg/d), Hydroxyzine (≤25mg/d) or antidepressants; 10. Lack of alcohol abuse or usage of forbidden substances; 11. Signed informed consent.

After clinical interview and confirmation of the diagnosis, the patients were examined via the following neuropsychological battery: Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE), Isaac's Set Test (IST for verbal fluency), Literal fluency Test (LFT; variant M-O-H-A in Bulgarian, 1 minute for every letter), Clock Drawing Test (CDT), 10 Words Test (for working memory, delayed recall and recognition (10/20words), Bulgarian variant), Digit Symbol Substitution test (DSST 90sec), Digit Span Test (DST forward and backward) and 21 Hamilton Depression Scale (HDS). All patients with HDS above 12 points were excluded.

The same neuropsychological battery was used 2 years after the first examination.

The statistical analysis was done via parametric and non-parametric tests as ANOVA, MANOVA, Man-Whitney and Kruskal-Wallis test statistics and simple regression analysis via SPSS 20.0 and Statgraphics 20.0. All results were interpreted at 95% confidential level (p 0.05).

Results:

1. Demographic data

Patients with anemia were slightly more elderly than those without (see table 1). Although females prevailed over males at both groups, the frequency of anemia among male patients with cognitive decline was higher. Interestingly, patients with anemia were slightly better educated than those without.

2. Correlation between anemia and cognitive functioning.

Patients with anemia showed lower MMSE, IST, LFT, CDT and DSST test results vs those without (see table 2). They also showed addition 2 years' delay on IST and DSST. We didn't find correlations between anemia and DST or memory (10WT).

3. Correlation between serum hemoglobin level and cognitive performances.

There were correlations between serum hemoglobin level and MMSE (reciprocal), IST (reciprocal), LFT (linear), CDT (sqr. root), DSST (sqr. root or linear) test performances (see table 3). We failed to find any correlations between serum hemoglobin level and DST or 10WT. We didn't find correlations between serum hemoglobin level and 2 years' delay on any examined scale.

Discussion:

The prevalence of mild anemia among our patients was 26%. It was more often in our male patients (29%) vs females (24%). It could be due to socio-economic purposes and our restrictive criteria (we excluded patients with moderate to severe dementia). However, our patients with anemia were slightly more elderly than those without and at such age prevailed females, which principally had better diet intake and better medical and social care than males in our country. Interestingly, anemia was more frequent in our high (26.5%) and middle (27.45%) educated patients than those with basic education (16.67%). This fact can be explained by our specific socio-economic factors such as living conditions (patients with basic education most often live in small villages and eat healthier food, that grow alone, which included meat and highly educated live in bigger towns and cities and depend on food supply from shops and commercial centers), sick patients with basic education have higher mortality rate (because of lack of sufficient medical care and delayed diagnosis), etc.

Our patients with anemia have lower global cognition, lower results on test for executive functioning (IST, LFT, DSST) and visual-special abilities than those without. The serum hemoglobin level also correlates with above mentioned scales. Although there

aren't correlations with memory itself. Such results are obtained from other authors (Gattas, 2020; Weiss, 2022; Fehsel, 2023). Anemia-associated cognitive impairments are comparatively mild and are significantly associated with the serum hemoglobin level, but not so much with the exact level of serum iron (Agrawal, 2019; Gattas, 2020). Multiple mechanisms of impact of anemia on cognitive dysfunction are suggested. The significant role might play the low hemoglobin level, Vitamin B12 deficiency and the other comorbidities (Gattas, 2020; Lei, 2021; Fehsel, 2023). One of the possible mechanism of impact is the mechanism of hypoxemia and lowering of blood flow into the brain which induces chronic inflammation, ischemia and oxidative stress with impaired amyloid clearance and worsening of small vessels' disease (Wolters, 2019; Gattas, 2020; Fonseca, 2021; Lei, 2021; Fehsel, 2023). Another potential mechanism of brain damage is associated with the level of erythropoietin and its receptors throughout the brain. Erythropoietin and its receptors play important protective role against neurodegeneration (Gattas, 2020). Low iron level is also associated with amyloid deposition and neurodegeneration at some specific conditions (Fehsel, 2023). Because of the vulnerability of deep white matter to hypoxia, the most impaired cognitive domain in cases with anemia is executive functioning, which is mostly associated with frontal and deep white matter dysfunctions (Andreev, 2020; Choi, 2020; Gattas, 2020; Weiss, 2022; Fehsel, 2023). We also find correlations mostly between executive functions and anemia (information processing speed and attention, but not cognitive inhibition and working memory). Interestingly, we failed to find any correlations between short term and long term memory (including retrieval from memory depos and recognition) and anemia which suggested partial preservation of temporal lobe functioning at least for short – periods of time. We also obtain additional visual-spatial disability in association with anemia, which also could be explained with deep white matter dysfunction but at most posterior brain regions (e.g. occipital and parietal lobes).

Conclusions: Anemia is frequent in elderly patients with cognitive deficits and dementia. The existence of anemia is associated with additional executive dysfunction in such patients.

Table 1

Demographic and clinical data								
	AD	VD	MD	Total	Age (years)	M:F	B:M:H	Hb (g/l)
Without anemia	27	44	27	108	75.55±7.39	34:74	10:61:37	136.66±12.79
With anemia	11	12	15	38	80.0±6.76	14:24	2:22:14	115.21±4.21
P					0.0014	0.0022	0.0349	0.0001
Total	38	56	52	146	76.71±7.47	48:98	12:83:51	130.12±17.05
Legend: AD – Alzheimer's disease; VD – vascular dementia, MD – mixed dementia; M:F – male:female ratio; B:M:H – with basic: with middle: with high education.								

Table 2

Correlations between anemia and cognitive performances of our patients with cognitive impairment and dementia.

The correlations between anemia and:	Average or mediana of patients without and with anemia	p=
MMSE 1 (p.)	NA	>0.05
MMSE 2 (p.)	25 vs 22	0.0232*
2 years MMSE delay (p.)	NA	>0.05
IST1 (p.)	NA	>0.05
IST2 (p.)	30 vs 26	0.0311*
2 years IST delay (p.)	-1.0 vs -3.0	0.0162*
LFT 1 (p.)	NA	>0.05
LFT 2 (p.)	21.04±10.98vs 15.44±10.06	0.0091
2 years LFT delay (p.)	NA	>0.05
CDT 1 (errors)	0.0 vs 1.0	0.0025*
CDT 2 (errors)	1.0 vs 3.0	0.0127*
2 years increasing of the number of errors on CDT.	NA	>0.05
DSST 1 (p.)	29.61±13.32 vs 24.29±13.01	0.0430
DSST 2 (p.)	25.96±14.57 vs 19.03±13.83	0.0156
2 years DSST delay (p.)	-2.0 vs -3.5	0.0485*

Legend: MMSE – Mini Mental State Examination; IST – Isaac’s Set Tes; LFT – Literal Fluency Test; CDT – Clock Drawing Test; DSST – Digit Symbol Substitution Test; 1- at first examination; 2 – 2 years after the first examination; * Kruskal-Wallis. Without * t-test. We excluded all scales without correlation with anemia.

Table 3

Regression analysis – the correlation between serum hemoglobin level and cognitive performances.

Regression analysis between the serum Hemoglobin level (g/l; X) on neuropsychological scales (Y):	rr	Model of correlation, p=
MMSE 1 (p.)	-0.20	reciprocal (X), p=0.0177
MMSE 2 (p.)	-0.22	reciprocal(X), p=0.0061
2 years MMSE delay (p.)	NA	>0.05
IST1 (p.)	NA	>0.05
IST2 (p.)	-0.20	reciprocal (X), p=0.0224
2 years IST delay (p.)	NA	>0.05
LFT 1 (p.)	0,25	linear, p=0.0050
LFT 2 (p.)	0,34	linear, p=0.0001
2 years LFT delay (p.)	NA	>0.05
CDT 1 (errors)	-0.23	Sqr root (Y), p=0.0075
CDT 2 (errors)	-0.21	Sqr root (Y), p=0,0138
2 years increasing of the number of errors on CDT.	NA	p>0.05
DSST 1 (p.)	0.21	Sqr root (X), p=0.0168
DSST 2 (p.)	0.26	linear, p=0.0032
2 years DSST delay (p.)	NA	>0.05

Legend: MMSE – Mini Mental State Examination; IST – Isaac’s Set Tes; LFT – Literal Fluency Test; CDT – Clock Drawing Test; DSST – Digit Symbol Substitution Test; 1- at first examination; 2 – 2 years after the first examination; rr – correlation coefficient

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